

The Impact of Health Electronic System on the Time Efficiency in Nursing Practice. An Integrative Review

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ABSTRACT

Background: shortage of nurses is a common challenge in nursing and healthcare with a few nurses working in overtime schedules to meet patients' demands. Therefore, the amount of time spent by nurses is of critical value to the healthcare organization as it is to patients. Improvements in healthcare technology, notably the introduction of nursing informatics, has tried to improve nursing practices with the goal of meeting efficient patient care. Consequently, researchers moved in to examine the significance of the electronic health systems, such as the electronic health records in improving efficiency of nurses' practices, and several diverse outcomes have been reported.

Objective: due to the divergent outcomes, this integrative review was designed to assess whether there were agreeing outcomes regarding the impact of health electronic system on time efficiency in nursing.

Methods and results: a total of ten literature articles obtained from PubMed and Google Scholar met the quality assessments and inclusion criteria and were thus included in this review. These articles were published in the last ten years in English and used primary data. All the articles used quantitative methodologies. The analysis of the individual study findings resulted in the construction of two thematic outcomes: the changes in the documentation time and improvement in nurses' work proficiency and clinical efficiency. Therefore, this review identified that electronic health systems had a significant effect in altering the documentation time in a nonspecific way. Also, the effect on nursing proficiency and clinical efficiency was definite.

Recommendation: there is a need to examine organizational factors that could affect time efficiency among of the electronic health systems.

KEYWORDS: nursing staff, electronic health records, computerized provider order entry, health information systems, nursing informatics, and time efficiency.

ARTICLE DETAILS

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INTRODUCTION

The amount of time spent by nurses in handling various clinical activities is of critical value to the healthcare organization as it is to patients too (Moore et al., 2020). There has been a problem of nurses' shortages in many nations and regions in the world, which highlights the need for cautious time usage (Drennan & Ross, 2019). Drennan and Ross (2019, p. 5) considered nurses' shortages as "the numbers of nurses required (demand for) against the future number available to work (the supply)" which indicates a

natural balance. Any imbalance between number of nurses and the available work thus indicates that the available nurses will require more time in handling clinical activities. Studies have also shown that one of the factors impacting the efficiency of nurses' work output, witnessed in patients' outcomes and limited errors, is burnout due to little time of resting (Shanafelt et al., 2010; Lewis, Baernholdt & Hamric, 2013; Al Balushi et al., 2021). Efficient time usage among nurses is thus highly valuable in nursing environment.

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Any approach that would limit any time wastage is thus highly valuable in improving nursing activities and clinical operations towards better patient care. One of the techniques with promising positive impact on reducing time wastages among nurses' activities is the use of electronic systems, such as the electronic health record (EHR) and computerized provider order entry (CPOE) systems (Sanders et al., 2014; Read-Brown, et al., 2013; Westbrook et al., 2013). Some researchers have reported that electronic systems help to improve the efficiency in patients' care by saving time spent on the various medication activities (McComas, Riingen & Kim, 2014). Time saving comes as a result of the redistribution of the time across many different medication activities. For instance, it becomes easier for nurses to modify the existing prescription orders than writing new ones while using the pen and papers design (Westbrook et al., 2013). At the same time, nurses and other healthcare workers would spend less time in reading (ease of orders' legibility).

However, there have been mixed results regarding the healthcare workers' perceptions towards the adoption of the electronic systems. While some studies report positive outcomes, others have indicated negative concerns on the adaptability (Georgiou et al., 2009; Westbrook et al., 2015; Baysari et al., 2020). Georgiou et al. (2009) identified that many different challenges against the successful adoption if the CPOE, including the adaptability of the software and hardware, easy of training and usage, inadequate skills, coping, and social concerns. At the same time, other researcher have noted that the introduction the electronic systems have resulted in improved identification of medication errors, efficiency in clinical operations, increased productivity among nurses and enhanced patient safety (Culler et al., 2011; Redley & Botti, 2013; Westbrook et al., 2015).

There is indeed a huge number of studies that already identified the significance of electronic health systems in tackling various clinical problems to improve the efficiency in nursing practices. However, the inconsistencies arising the benefits and challenges elucidate the need for a comprehensive examination of these studies and to synthesize the outcomes and to identify the adoptable outcomes for nursing practice. Therefore, this integrative

review examines the impact of health electronic system on time efficiency in nursing.

PROBLEM AND SIGNIFICANCE

Currently, there is a widespread adoption and use of electronic health records to improve the overall flow of healthcare operations. The use of health electronic systems is expected to improve efficiency in patient care and help in managing time among the healthcare workers, notably nurses. Accordingly, many research studies have been conducted to examine the significance of health electronic systems in improving time efficiency among nurses; however, the outcomes are too diverse and inconclusive. Even the previous systematic reviews have not conclusively and implicitly identified the benefits of electronic health systems in improving time efficiency among nurses (Moore et al., 2020; Yen & Bakken, 2012). With the increasing adoption of these systems in healthcare, and with the unending technological advancements, there is a significant need of understanding the impact of electronic health technology in improving time efficiency in nursing.

METHODS AND QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Articles were sought from two freely-available online journal database sources; PubMed and Google Scholar. The search was guided by specific key words; 'nurse' OR 'nursing staff' AND 'electronic health records', OR 'computerized provider order entry' OR 'health information systems' OR 'nursing informatics' AND 'time efficiency'. Importantly, the literature search was guided by specific criteria. First, only the article published in the last 10 years (between 2011 and 2021) were included. The other criteria included the peer reviews journal articles published in English and having the primary data. As such, all other types of reviews were excluded from this integrative review. Moreover, the resultant articles were further scrutinized for quality regarding the internal validity, thoroughness of the research methods and relevance of the results. Quality of the articles were examined according to their scholarliness and methodological techniques.

The summary of the articles' search is summarized in the PRISMA diagram, Figure 1.

Figure 1. A PRISMA diagram showing a summary of the article’s selection process

RESULTS

A total of ten (10) articles were identified that addressed the impact of electronic health systems in improving time efficiency in nursing. The summary of the articles is

provided in Table 1 indicating the authors, study purpose, sample size, design and main findings for each study. Nevertheless, it is important to note that there is a scanty research articles published in this topic.

SUMMARY TABLE

Table 1. data abstraction table

Authors (Year)	Title	Purpose	Sample size	Design	Main findings
Cho et al. (2016):	Comparing usability testing outcomes and functions of six electronic nursing record systems.	To examine the usability of six differing electronic nursing record (ENR) systems on the efficiency, proficiency and available functions for documenting nursing care	54 staff nurses from six hospitals	Quantitative cross-sectional research design	The mean competency index was 59.5%, mean efficiency score was 94.2% and the mean proficiency was 60.6%. There was a positive association between efficiency scores and time to complete the tasks.
Westbrook et al. (2013):	Impact of an electronic medication management system on hospital doctors' and nurses' work: a	To quantify and compare the time spent by doctors and nurses on direct patient care, medication related tasks, and	70 nurses and 59 doctors	A controlled pre-post, time and motion study	Nurses spent lesser time with the doctors after introducing the electronic medication management system (p=.0001).

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Authors (Year)	Title	Purpose	Sample size	Design	Main findings
	controlled pre–post, time and motion study.	interactions before and after the introduction of the electronic medication management system.			
Karp et al. (2019):	Changes in efficiency and quality of nursing electronic health record documentation after implementation of an admission patient history essential data set	To evaluate whether electronic health record system timers and event logs can measure the efficiency and quality of a clinical process in an electronic health record.	Pre-intervention assessment (n=536) and post-intervention (n=640).	Pre and post-nonrandomized prospective cohort design	Capture of essential data elements improved by almost 6%, and admission patient history data completed in one sequence increased by 24%.
Schenk et al. (2018):	Impact of adoption of a comprehensive electronic health record on nursing work and caring efficacy.	To investigate the impacts of adoption of a comprehensive electronic health record by measuring nursing locations and interventions before adoption and 12 months post adoption.	Pre-adoption sample (n=40) and post-adoption sample (n=44).	Observational study	The introduction of comprehensive electronic health record brought about the difference in observed nurses location, time spent on different locations and time spent on different interventions.
Dowding, Turley & Garrido (2012):	The impact of an electronic health record on nurse sensitive patient outcomes: an interrupted time series analysis.	To evaluate the impact of electronic health record (EHR) implementation on nursing care processes and outcomes.	29 hospitals in Northern and Southern California	Interrupted time series analysis	The introduction of EHR lead to increase in the documentation for Hospital acquired pressure ulcers and 13% decrease in HAPU rates.
Vehko et al. (2019):	Experienced time pressure and stress: electronic health records usability and information technology competence play a role	To examine EHR usability factors and nurses' informatics competence factors related to self-reported time pressure and psychological distress.	3607 registered nurses.	Nationwide survey	Low EHR reliability and poor user-friendliness were associated with high time pressure. Low EHR reliability and low support for cooperation predicted the high psychological distress among nurses. Low e-Care competence was associated with high psychological distress.
Munyisia, Yu & Hailey (2011):	Does the introduction of an electronic nursing documentation system in a nursing home reduce time on	To examine where the introduction of EHR could decrease the proportion of time nursing staff spend on documentation.	383 activities	Observational study	The proportion of time on documentation only improved after 6 th month, but went back to the original after 12 th month.

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Authors (Year)	Title	Purpose	Sample size	Design	Main findings
	documentation for the nursing staff?				
Munyisia, Yu & Hailey (2012):	The impact of an electronic nursing documentation system on efficiency of documentation by caregivers in a residential aged care facility	To examine the effects of the introducing electronic nursing documentation system on the efficiency of documentation in a residential aged care facility.	1594 documentation activities	Longitudinal cohort study	The proportion of time caregivers spent on documentation reduced 3 months after the implementation, increased from six months then dropped after 23 months. Recreational activity officers' proportion increased at three months after implementation.
Read-Brown et al. (2013):	Time-motion analysis of clinical nursing documentation during implementation of an electronic operating room management system for ophthalmic surgery.	To examine the effect of introducing Electronic Health Records on clinical nursing documentation.	A single ophthalmology unit	Time-motion study	EHR nursing documentation time was poorest at the early implementation, but improved to a level near but slightly worse than paper baseline. The mean documentation time varied significantly among nurses during early implementation. There was no decrease in operating room turnover time or surgical volume after implementation.
Sanders et al. (2014):	Impact of an electronic health record operating room management system in ophthalmology on documentation time, surgical volume, and staffing.	To determine the impact of an EHR OR management system on intraoperative nursing documentation time, surgical volume, and staffing requirements.	Nurses (n = 13) and surgeons (n = 25) in a single ophthalmology unit.	Prospective cohort design	The percentage of operating time documenting and absolute mean documentation time worsened in the early periods before improving in the late periods. There were no significant differences in the overall staffing requirements and surgical volume.

CONCLUDED THEMES

A total of ten peer-reviews research articles were retrieved for the analysis as presented in the data abstraction table (Cho et al., 2016; Westbrook et al., 2013; Karp et al., 2019; Schenk et al., 2018; Dowding, Turley & Garrido, 2012; Vehko et al., 2019; Munyisia, Yu & Hailey, 2011; Munyisia, Yu & Hailey, 2012; Read-Brown et al., 2013;

Sanders et al., 2014). From the included articles, it was noted that all the research studies applied quantitative methodologies. Moreover, the included articles met the inclusion criteria and possessed adequate qualities for inclusion for this integrative review.

From the analysis of the study outcomes, two significant themes were noted in relation to the impact of

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health electronic system on time efficiency for nursing. These themes include the changes in time on documentation and improvement in nurses' work proficiency and clinical efficiency. These themes are discussed below:

a) Changes in Documentation Time

Reduction in time of documenting the clinical information, records and data was widespread outcome among the included research studies. A total of four research articles indicated that the use or introduction of the health electronic system was effective in reducing time spent by clinical nurses in documenting patients' clinical information (Munyisia, Yu & Hailey, 2011; Munyisia, Yu & Hailey, 2012; Read-Brown et al., 2013; Sanders et al., 2014). The outcomes was noted from diverse populations, and in different geographical areas.

Sanders et al. (2014) observed that percentage of operating time documenting, at first, worsened even more than the baseline when the EHR was freshly implemented. However, in the later periods, the percentage of operating time documenting reduced (from 16.7 minutes to 9.2 minutes) upon the application of the EHR. Nevertheless, this research did not report any positive impact of the EHR on the cataract procedures required per nurse. The changes in documentation time was thus noted to improve with time. The improvements in the documentation time was also reported among the nurses working in another single ophthalmology unit by Read-Brown et al. (2013). However, the trends in time changes was slightly different. According to Read-Brown et al. (2013), the documentation time only slightly reduced during the late implementation phase but not steady. Moreover, these researchers noted that "there was no decrease in operating room turnover time or surgical volume after implementation" (p. 4548).

In another research study conducted by Munyisia, Yu and Hailey (2012), the documentation time fluctuated significantly over the period of implementation from the third month to two years. At first, these researchers noted that the proportion of time that the caregivers spent on documentation started to reduce at the third months upon the implementation of the EHR. However, by the sixth month, there were increases in the documentation time. By the 23rd month, the documentation time reduced again. This kind of fluctuation was also reported by Munyisia, Yu and Hailey (2011) who examined, through an observational research, whether the introduction of the EHR could lead to a significant decrease in the documentation time among the clinical nurses. According to Munyisia, Yu and Hailey (2011), the proportion of time on documentation did not change by the third month. There was a significant improvement observed by the sixth month, which later reverted back to the baseline level after 12th month. In this case, the fluctuations were only observed in the short periods of time. Therefore, it is evident that the introduction of the EHR leads to significant changes in the documentation time for different time periods.

b) Improvement in Nurses' Work Proficiency and Clinical Efficiency

Efficiency in the operation of nurses and the outcomes observed among the clinical operations was also reported by some studies. A total of six research studies confirmed the significance of the EHR in enhancing clinical nurses operations and the efficiency of care practices (Cho et al., 2016; Westbrook et al., 2013; Karp et al., 2019; Schenk et al., 2018; Dowding, Turley & Garrido, 2012; Vehko et al., 2019). These outcomes concur among different research studies conducted in different geographical areas, and by using different samples.

Cho et al. (2016) examined the usability of six differing electronic nursing record (ENR) systems for their efficiency, proficiency and available functions to enable the documentation of nursing care among registered nurses, and noted a high efficiency score (94.2%). Similarly, it was noted that the application of the six systems improved nurses operations alongside improved usability. However, Cho et al. (2016) reported that usability of the electronic systems was affected by nurses' demographic characteristics, such as age, clinical experience and level of education. According to the controlled pre-post, time and motion study research by Westbrook et al. (2013), there was a significant improvement in the nurses' operations based on the time spent in sharing information with the doctors. The study outcomes confirmed that nurses spent lesser time with the doctors upon the introduction of the electronic medication management system (Westbrook et al, 2013, p. 1150).

Another concept of nurses' operational efficiency was reported regarding the use of clinical information. The introduction of the electronic health systems improved the access and usability of the clinical data and patients' information (Karp et al., 2019; Cho et al., 2016). The nonrandomized prospective cohort research conducted by Karp et al. (2019) found out that the electronic health record system improved nurses' efficacy and use of significant clinical and patient information processing by 24%. Similarly, Cho et al. (2016) indicated that the adoption of differing electronic nursing records improved nurses' competency and proficiency by 59.5% and 60.6% respectively. These outcomes points towards the significance of the electronic health systems in improving nurses' operations and clinical competencies.

Other researchers have also noted that the use of electronic health record systems improve the care for specific diseases and convenience among nurses (Dowding, Turley & Garrido, 2012; Vehko et al., 2019; Schenk et al., 2018). One of the studies reported that the introduction of the electronic health records lead to a significant improvements in the care for patients with hospital-acquired pressure ulcers by 13% (Dowding, Turley & Garrido, 2012). Moreover, Schenk et al. (2018) noted that the introduction of comprehensive electronic health record resulted in saved

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the time spent by nurses in different intervention units in the hospital. In the same line, Vehko et al. (2019) reported that the absence or lower applications of the electronic-care competencies has a significant effect on the level of psychological distress among clinical nurses.

IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This review identified that the use of electronic health records has diverse significance in healthcare and in promoting nurses duties and patient care activities. Overall there are many positive outcomes reported, which encourage the adoption of electronic health systems, such as the EHR in healthcare. Notably, there are several related studies to the current topic of inquiry that examined the benefits of electronic health systems in improving healthcare operations, which elicits the need for more integrated assessment of the overall significance of electronic health systems.

This review noted that there is a missing consensus regarding the impact of electronic health systems in improving time efficacy among nurses. While some studies reported positive outcomes in a short period of time (as less as three months), other did not observe any significant improvements in nurses' time even after two years. In fact, it can be noted that the results of studies assessing the impact of health electronic system on time efficiency in nursing are highly affected by time. For the same reason, time-motion studies have been adopted in nursing research. Interestingly, even the time-motion studies also report different patterns of effect, which could be confounded by other institution-based factors.

The wide variations time efficiency assessments calls for more studies to assess the impact of health electronic system on time efficiency in nursing. The studies also need to factor in the institution-based factors, such as organizational structure, culture and even leadership style since these factors also affect time efficiency parallel to the technology adoption. Moreover, there is a need to examine other nursing efficiency indicators of the electronic health systems in addition to time.

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